

THE ROLE OF GAME TECHNOLOGIES AND THEIR APPLICATION IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract: The article defines the role of gaming technologies and their active use in foreign language lessons. The functions and advantages of forms of teaching in the educational process in a foreign language are also revealed. Much attention is paid to the classification of language and speech games.

Keywords: *game, gaming technologies, didactic games, role-playing games*

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается роль игровых технологий и их активное применение на уроках иностранного языка. Также раскрываются функции и ценность игровых форм обучения в учебно-воспитательном процессе по иностранному языку. Большое внимание отводится классификации языковых и речевых игр.

Ключевые слова: *игра, игровые технологии, дидактические игры, ролевые игры*

Annotatsiya: Maqolada o'yin texnologiyalarining roli va ulardan chet tili darslarida faol foydalanishi ko'rib chiqiladi. Chet tilidagi o'quv jarayonida o'qitishning o'yin shakllarining vazifalari va ahamiyati ham ochib berilgan. Til va nutq o'yinlarining tasnifiga katta e'tibor beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: *o'yin, o'yin texnologiyalari, didaktik o'yinlar, rolli o'yinlar*

Play as a method of learning and transferring social experience has been used since ancient times. In modern schools, play activities are used by teachers:

- as an independent technology for mastering a concept, topic, and even a section of an academic subject;
- as an element of a more general technology;
- as a lesson or part of it (introduction, control);
- as a technology for extracurricular activities.

G.K. Selevko gives the following definition of gaming technology: “this is a type of activity in situations aimed at recreating and assimilating social experience, in which self-government of behavior is formed and improved” [3, 256].

The concept of “game pedagogical technologies” includes a fairly extensive group of methods and techniques for organizing the pedagogical process in the form of various pedagogical games. Unlike games in general, a pedagogical game has an essential feature - a clearly defined learning goal and a corresponding pedagogical result, which can be

justified, identified explicitly and characterized by an educational-cognitive orientation [2, 140–146].

Gaming technologies contribute to the actualization of various motives for educational activities, primarily such as:

- motives for communication;
- moral motives;
- cognitive motives

The motivation of gaming activity is ensured by its voluntariness, opportunities for choice and elements of competition, satisfaction of needs, self-affirmation, and self-realization.

We propose to classify games used in foreign language lessons into two main groups:

1. Didactic games, which include grammatical, lexical, phonetic and spelling games that contribute to the development of students’ speech skills. Unlike games in general, a didactic game has an essential feature - a clearly defined learning goal and a corresponding result, which can be justified, identified explicitly and characterized by an educational-cognitive orientation. In and through didactic play, players must learn something. The didactic game is characterized by the following: – connection with a specific educational goal;

- the ability to repeat, interrupt or start again at any time;
- openness, i.e. the end of the game is not precisely defined;
- satisfaction from participation, lack of “consequences” for those playing (this activity should not be evaluated in any way).

In our opinion, the fundamental difference between didactic games and exercises and tasks is that:

Firstly, there is no set pattern of behavior in the game, and the participant himself chooses a possible variant of verbal interaction and evaluates the result of its implementation. The only limiter on the content and form of the game is the educational material (lesson topic, goal, planned results).

Secondly, the game, as a rule, is competitive. A student, entering into relationships with playing partners, evaluates his strength not only in comparison with other players. The game allows him to objectively assess his capabilities.

Thirdly, in the game, schoolchildren learn interpersonal and group communication and learn to choose the optimal means of resolving (linguistic and non-linguistic) conflict situations.

G. Heyd divides didactic games used in foreign language classes into two large groups: 1) “games with language material” and 2) “games in language” [4]. The first corresponds to activities aimed at systematizing language material. In this case, much attention is paid to knowledge of grammatical rules. Therefore, such games are well suited for training at the initial stage, but also for training individual structures at an advanced stage. Games with language material can be fully programmed and therefore controlled.

The author notes that “the closed nature of games and the leading role of the teacher become the reason for the unsuitability of games of this kind for conversation practice lessons” [5]. But this does not mean that they cannot be successfully used for certain purposes.

Creative role-playing games are one of the ways to learn foreign languages. Concepts such as role-playing, simulation, drama, and play are often used interchangeably, but they have different meanings. When simulating, students play their natural role, in other words, the role they play in real life (for example, the role of a buyer or booking transport tickets). In role-playing games, students play a role that they do not play in real life (for example, a prime minister or a rock star). A role-playing game can be considered as one of the components or elements of a simulation. Thus, in role-playing, participants assign roles that they act out within a scenario. Simulation focuses on the interaction of one role with other roles rather than on the enactment of individual roles.

In turn, role-playing games can be classified as follows:

1. Short-term role-playing game, which is the simplest and fastest type of game, lasting from 10 to 30 minutes. It can be based on text or dialogue. An example of this game can be presented in the form of an interview. Students are divided into pairs, after which they are given pictures depicting various problem situations (environmental pollution, deforestation, lack of food in zoos). One of the students takes the role of the interviewer, the other the role of the respondent.

The task is to describe the problem and propose a solution. The game component is that experts are also appointed among the students, whose task is to create criteria for evaluation and subsequently evaluate all speakers and point out mistakes made.

2. A full-fledged role-playing game in which students are provided with a description of the situation and their roles. The duration of this type of game takes on average one or two lessons. As an example, consider verbal role-playing games.

One of the most famous board word games is Mafia. The role-playing game "Mafia" is very popular all over the world, and you can play it both in class and in extracurricular activities using the Internet. Students, paying attention to the progress of the game, begin to speak spontaneously. The use of this game as part of the lesson helps students develop their communicative competence, teaches them to defend their point of view, persuade and encourages them to take initiative.

3. Computer role-playing games. Nowadays, it is difficult to imagine a person unfamiliar with computer role-playing games. For those teachers whose students have easy access to the Internet, computer role-playing games may be a good choice. These games give interested students the opportunity to make direct contact with people from all over the world who have common interests but who must use English to communicate, thus emphasizing the value of language learning beyond school grades. Most computer role-playing games have the ability to train both listening and reading skills.

Thus, gaming technologies occupy an important place in the educational process. The wide range of role-playing games allows them to be used in any part of the

curriculum. At the same time, they are a very useful tool that makes learning a foreign language interesting and memorable. Role-playing games provide a positive emotional state for students and a communicative focus of the lesson.

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